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D6.6 – Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 Report

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
BC2026	Blue-Cloud 2026
DGRTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission)
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HE	Horizon Europe
KER	Key Exploitable Result
VLab	Virtual Lab
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
WP	Work Package

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The [Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025](#) is a collaborative event organised in the framework of Work Package 6 (“Outreach, Engagement, and Education) of the Horizon Europe “**Blue-Cloud 2026**” project, which aims to promote and disseminate Key Exploitable Results (KER) stemming from the project to key target audiences. The main objective of the hackathon is to bring together scientists, researchers, developers, and innovators to explore and test the open science environment evolved by the Blue-Cloud 2026 project and its related services. The hackathon serves as a gateway to promote the Blue-Cloud open science platform and services to diverse marine and environmental communities, encourage the testing, adoption, and further development of Blue-Cloud services, and collect valuable user feedback to improve available services.

The event took place in **September – October 2025** and brought together over one thousand participants from across the globe for a dynamic, fully virtual, hands-on innovation experience. Designed as an inclusive and collaborative event, the hackathon welcomed marine scientists, data experts, software developers, students, and ocean enthusiasts to work together in multidisciplinary teams. A total of **1,140 participants** registered for the hackathon, and 348 successfully joined effort in forming **70 eligible teams** across 4 challenges, namely: (1) Mapping and Understanding Marine Ecosystems and Species; (2) Supporting Early Warning and Response to Accidents or Natural Events; (3) Tracking and Forecasting Ocean Health; (4) Wild Card: Team up with EDITO.

Teams represented an impressive mix of scientific, technical, and creative expertise, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of the Blue-Cloud community. Participants were invited to explore and combine the powerful data, models, and services provided by the Blue-Cloud platform and the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO) initiative. The hackathon served as a real-world testbed for the Blue-Cloud 2026 project’s federated, FAIR-compliant architecture, which integrates diverse marine data sources and analytical tools within a Virtual Research Environment (VRE). Three Teams were awarded winners of the event.

By leveraging cutting-edge digital infrastructures — including Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs, Thematic Workbenches, and interoperable data access services — participants were empowered to develop innovative, data-driven solutions addressing critical ocean challenges, from biodiversity loss and marine pollution to ecosystem monitoring and climate resilience. These technical components enabled real-time experimentation, prototyping, and co-development of workflows, using harmonised datasets and reusable analytical tools. The event not only demonstrated the growing maturity of the Blue-Cloud 2026 ecosystem but also reinforced its core mission: to accelerate open science, foster cross-sector collaboration, and drive digital innovation for sustainable ocean management. Through community engagement and co-creation, the hackathon showcased the potential of core and thematic services deployed by the Blue-Cloud 2026 project to support both EU policy objectives and global marine research efforts.

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1. About the Blue-Cloud Hackathon and this report

The [Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025](#) is a collaborative event organised in the framework of Work Package 6 (“Outreach, Engagement, and Education) of the Horizon Europe (HE) “**Blue-Cloud 2026**” project, which aims to promote and disseminate Key Exploitable Results (KER) stemming from the project to key target audiences. The main objective of the hackathon is to bring together scientists, researchers, developers, and innovators to explore and test the open science environment evolved by the Blue-Cloud 2026 project and its related services. The hackathon serves as a gateway to:

- Promote the **Blue-Cloud open science platform** to diverse marine and environmental communities.
- Encourage the **testing, adoption, and further development** of Blue-Cloud services.
- Collect **valuable user feedback** to improve available services.

Held virtually from **29 September to 2 October 2025**, the hackathon invited participants to experiment with Blue-Cloud 2026’s Virtual Labs, Workbenches, and analytical tools to develop innovative, data-driven applications addressing ocean-related challenges. The event was hosted as on [online hackathon](#).

This Report provides an overview of the event and the results. **Section 2** offers a short summary of the event structure and the process towards its delivery. **Section 3** provides a snapshot of its key results. A fully comprehensive, visual summary of the event is included as an **Annex** to this Report.

Figure 1: Promotional banner for the Blue Cloud Hackathon 2025

2. Event structure and process towards delivery

2.1. Event phases and challenges

The **Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025** was set up as an **online event**, featuring 3 distinctive milestones:

- A 2-week training, ideation & mentorship phase (held 16-24 Sep 2025).
- A 3-day hackathon competition (29 Sep - 1 Oct 2025).
- A Final Pitch & Award Ceremony (held on 2 Oct 2025).

Participants were invited to form teams to develop innovative applications to address specific challenges using Blue-Cloud services, encouraging creativity and cross-disciplinary collaboration. The challenges presented included:

- **Challenge 1: Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystems and Species:** Use collaborative science and marine datasets to map and analyse species distribution, traits, and ecosystem dynamics using at least two Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs or Workbenches.
- **Challenge 2: Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents or Natural Events:** Develop tools to predict, monitor, and respond to risks such as invasive species, oil spills, or aquaculture impacts using integrated coastal and ocean observation data.
- **Challenge 3: Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health:** Apply environmental indicators to detect and forecast changes in marine ecosystems, including pollution dispersion, thermal trends, and eutrophication patterns.
- **Challenge 4 – Wild Card: Double up with EDITO:** Leverage the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO) infrastructure alongside Blue-Cloud resources to address any ocean challenge of choice using open data and digital models.

2.2. Communications towards onboarding participants

A communication campaign was set up to promote the Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 combining targeted social media outreach, digital advertising, and academic network engagement. The campaign emphasised the inclusive nature of Blue-Cloud, inviting both experienced data users and newcomers to explore open marine data.

The campaign successfully amplified awareness across Europe and beyond. A dedicated **Meta** (Facebook) campaign achieved strong results, reaching over 463,000 users and generating 1.6 million impressions. It resulted in 8,000 page views and 1,800 registration clicks, achieving a 1.10% click-through rate and €0.14 cost-per-click. Complementary email campaigns reached over 15,000 contacts, including marine science departments, innovation hubs, and data science communities.

Organic communication supported visibility through storytelling — spotlighting mentors, previous hackathon alumni, and Blue-Cloud 2026 tools. This holistic approach resulted in 1,140 total registrations from diverse backgrounds and regions.

2.3. Registration and team formation

A total of **1,140 participants** registered for the hackathon, of which **348** successfully formed **70 eligible teams** across the four challenges. A full overview of the Teams registered in the hackathon is available at the event page: <https://eventornado.com/event/blue-cloud-hackathon-2025#home>. Further information on the composition of the finalist Teams is provided in **Section 3** of this report.

Registration data

Teams registered: 118
 Participants registered: 1140

Eligible teams: 70
 Teams per challenge:

- 1 - 21 teams
- 2 - 25 teams
- 3 - 19 teams
- 4 - 5 teams

Participants in eligible teams: 348

Teams who submitted all deliverables: 22
 Participants of the above teams: 131

Figure 2: Blue Cloud hackathon 2025 Registration Data¹

2.4. Supporting participants with Coaches & Mentors

An expert team of over **30 Mentors and Coaches** composed of Team members of the **Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium** played a pivotal role in guiding participants throughout the hackathon, as members of the event’s **Coaching & Mentoring Team** (see Figure 4).

¹ Registrations were received from Europe and beyond, notably including from countries like India (23%) due to initial academic enrolment of full classes of students. Such registrations did not follow through with the formation of teams, which explains the difference between registrations (1140) and validated participants (348).

Name	Role	Organisation/Work title
Cyrielle Delvenne	Challenge Leader	Marine Project & Data Manager - Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
Jean-Olivier Irisson	Challenge Leader	Associate professor at Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Julia Vera	Challenge Leader	Lead Manager Business & Strategy at Seascope Belgium
Simona Simoncelli	Challenge Leader	Researcher at INGV
Bastien Grasset	Coach	Fisheries Research engineer at IRD (French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development)
Enrico Baglione	Coach	Researcher at INGV
Francesco Palermo	Coach	Senior Research Assistant at the CMCC Foundation
Juan Gabriel Fernández Pineda	Coach	Head of Data Center and Software Developer at SOCIB
Marco Lettere	Coach	Chair and CTO at Nubisware
Mauro Mugnaini	Coach	Nubisware S.r.l
Nydia Catalina Reyes Suarez	Coach	Research Technologist at the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
Paul Weerheim	Coach	Software Developer at Maris
Robin Kooyman	Coach	Software Developer at Maris
Sebastian Mieruch	Coach	Researcher, Software Developer at Alfred Wegener Institute
Vânia Lima	Coach	Researcher, Software Developer at Instituto Hidrografico (IH)
Victoria Bancel	Coach	Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Alexandre Schickele	Coach + Mentor	Postdoctoral researcher at ETH Zürich
Felix Dols	Coach + Mentor	Civil engineer at Deltares
Rafael Gomes de Menezes	Coach + Mentor	Research Assistant at CMCC
Joao Vitorino	Mentor	Oceanographer at Instituto Hidrografico (IH)
Josephine Broussin	Mentor	Postdoc at ETHZ
Matteo Bazzaro	Mentor	Permanent Researcher at the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
Megan Anne French	Mentor	Researcher at National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
Merlin Weiss	Mentor	PhD Student at ETH Zurich
Salvatore Causio	Mentor	Senior Researcher at CMCC
Sarah Hasnain	Mentor	Post-doctoral researcher at Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Virginie Sonnet	Mentor	Post-doctoral researcher at Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Abel Dechenne	Mentor + Coach	PhD Candidate at the University of Liège
Alexander Barth	Mentor + Coach	Associate Professor at the University of Liège
Julien Barde	Mentor + Coach	IT research engineer at IRD (French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development)

Figure 3: Blue Cloud Hackathon 2025 Registration Data

Mentors provided domain expertise across marine science, data analytics, ocean modelling, and user requirements. They offered technical advice on API usage, data harmonisation, workflow design, visualisation, and performance optimisation, ensuring that teams could fully leverage Blue-Cloud’s thematic services and its federated infrastructure. Several coaches provided support to guide participants in the use of Blue-Cloud’s core and thematic services. A number of coaches involved in the deployment of [EDITO](#) were added to the Team. This Mentoring & Coaching Team was critical to guide participants in addressing the proposed challenges, and helping teams translate scientific ideas into robust, interoperable prototypes, harnessing available services and resources.

Figure 4: Screenshot of a Blue Cloud Hackathon 2025 Preparation Team Meeting

2.5. Appointing Judges

A jury of independent experts was carefully assembled to ensure a fair and balanced evaluation of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 projects. The panel brought together a diverse mix of marine science, data, digital innovation, and blue economy expertise, with some of them being members of the Blue-Cloud 2026 External Stakeholder Expert Board (ESEB). The hackathon Judges assessed each project based on four key criteria: innovation, scientific merit, societal relevance, and effective use of Blue-Cloud and EDITO resources.

The 2025 jury members were:

- Elisa Ravagnan, NORCE, ESEB Member
- Marco Filippone, Fugro, ESEB Member
- Dave Mills, Bangor University, former member of the ESEB for Blue-Cloud pilot project
- Mary Malicet, Mercator Ocean International
- Othman Cherkaoui Dekkaki, ECOP Morocco Steering Committee, ESEB Member

This cross-disciplinary panel ensured that the winning teams were selected through a rigorous and informed process, aligned with the objectives of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.

2.6. Delivering Phase 1: Live Warm-Up sessions

A comprehensive programme of [live warm-up sessions](#) (16-24 September) introduced participants to the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform, its services, and the hackathon workflow. These sessions were designed not only to equip participants with the necessary technical knowledge but also to inspire and build confidence for the ideation process. These events were attended by hundreds of unique viewers and included interactive Q&As and polls.

1. Live Session 1: Welcome! Blue-Cloud Essentials

 12 Q&As

This session welcomed participants, introduced the Blue-Cloud Hackathon journey, and provided essential context, tools, and motivation. It covered the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, the Virtual Research Environment (VRE), Ocean Best Practices, and how to participate effectively – even without an initial idea.

2. Live Session 2: Explore the Virtual Labs

 4 Q&As

Participants were guided through the five thematic Virtual Labs. Coaches presented the tools and were available for direct Q&A with participants to clarify how to use the V Labs in their projects.

3. Live Session 3: Explore the Workbenches and Data Tools

 8 Q&As

This hands-on session (see Figure 5) provided a detailed demonstration of the Blue-Cloud Workbenches for Eutrophication, Physics, and Ecosystems, along with other key tools such as the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service, Beacon, and webODV.

4. Live Session 4: Get Familiar with the Hackathon Challenges

 1 Q&A

Challenge leaders presented the four main challenges in depth, providing context, objectives, and relevant Blue-Cloud/EDITO tools. This helped participants choose a track that matched their interests and skills.

Challenge leaders presented the four hackathon tracks in depth, providing context, objectives, and related tools to help participants select the challenge best aligned with their skills and interests.

Figure 5: Snapshot of the Blue Cloud Hackathon 2025 Live Online Warm-Up Session 3

2.7. Delivering Phase 2: Hackathon Kick-Off and resource pack

Hackathon Kick-Off Session

A live session hosted on 29 September officially launched the hackathon. It featured participant polls, further guidance from organisers, and motivational messaging to energise the teams as they began their collaborative work. The live event was opened by *Emina Mamaca (DG RTD)*, highlighting the importance of co-creation and digital innovation for ocean science and policy.

Resource Pack

Adding to the resources provided during the live, warm-up sessions (phase 1) and the hackathon kick-off, participants were given access to a **comprehensive Resource Pack** that included:

- Technical documentation, tutorials, and data access instructions.
- Overviews of the Blue-Cloud 2026 core and thematic services.
- Step-by-step guidance on using the VRE.
- EDITO hack pack.

This combination of live support and on-demand materials ensured that all participants, regardless of experience level, had the tools and support needed to fully engage with the Blue-Cloud ecosystem and maximise their hackathon experience.

Online Hackathon

Participants were given a 2-day framework (29 September – 1 October) to advance their solutions, following the [key milestones and requirements defined](#). At the end of this period, the Challenge Leaders appointed by the Blue-Cloud 2026 consortium evaluated all the deliverables submitted by the different participating teams, **shortlisting 10 Teams** for evaluation by the hackathon appointed Judges.

2.8. Delivering the Pitching & Award Ceremony

The final pitching session took place on 2 October and featured dynamic live presentations from the **top 10 teams shortlisted** for evaluation by the Blue-Cloud Hackathon Judges. Each team had the opportunity to pitch their project (for pitches, see Section 3). The Judges engaged directly with the Team Leaders, posing targeted questions about the scientific relevance, technical approach, and scalability of their solutions. After careful deliberation, the Judges selected **three winning teams** whose projects best demonstrated a combination of **innovation, feasibility, and potential, real-world impact**. The Hackathon finalists and winners are outlined in Section 3.

3. Results

3.1. Overall participation and Teams formed

A total of **1,140 participants** registered for the hackathon, forming **70 eligible teams** across the four challenges. Of these, **22 completed all deliverables by the deadline**. Teams represented an impressive mix of scientific, technical, and creative expertise, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of the Blue-Cloud community.

3.2. Finalist Teams

Following the evaluation of the deliverables², 10 multidisciplinary teams advanced to the final stage of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, representing a diverse mix of researchers, students, and professionals from across Europe and beyond. The finalist teams brought expertise ranging from marine science and modelling to data analytics and technology development.

² The full overview of the points assigned by the Judges to the different Teams is (internally) [available in this file](#)

Finalist teams

Figure 6: Blue Cloud Hackathon 2025 Finalist Teams

A consolidated list of each finalist team including the names, countries, and organisational affiliations of their members is provided below, illustrating the strong international and collaborative dimension of the hackathon.

Blue Cloud Hackathon 2025 Finalist Teams

Team Name	Team Member Name	Country	Organisation
TwinTrack	Ahmad Moko	Netherlands	Wageningen University and Research
	Natalie Klinard	Germany	GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel
	Ross McGill	Ireland	Loughs Agency

Blue-Cloud Marine	Samuel Fooks	Belgium	VLIZ
	Christopher Monk	Germany	Geomar Helmholtz centre for ocean research kiel
	Lotte Pohl	Belgium	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
	Laura Ballesteros	Colombia	National University of Colombia
	Michael Inso	Qatar	Worldmovers Inc
	Maria Arredondo	Spain	University of Algarve
	Dhanvanth GS	India	Chennai Institute Of Technology
	Dharsan T R	India	Chennai institute of technology
	Rathish Kumar R	India	Chennai institute of technology
	KAVIYAN A ECE	India	Chennai Institute of Technology
	MOHANACHANDHIRA N P	India	Chennai institute of technology
MOHAMED ILYAAS K M ECE	India	Chennai institute of technology	

	MONISHKUMAR M ECE	India	Chennai institute of technology
	KENSTON PINTO A ECE	India	Chennai Institute of technology
	MADHESH B ECE	India	Chennai institute of technology
RugOBSS	Maria J. Lima	Portugal	Centre for Marine and Environmental Research (CIMA)
	Mar Roca Mora	Spain	CSIC
	Bede Ffinian Rowe Davies	France	Nantes Université
Smiley axolotl	Martyna Hajduk	Belgium	Karel de Grote University of Applied Sciences and Arts in Antwerp
	Alec Tuffin	Belgium	Karel De Groote Hoogeschool
	Qosai Abu Ahmed	Belgium	kdg
	Alina Dimova	Belgium	Kdg
	Eva Reichel	Germany	KdG
	Daniil Mumladze	Belgium	Karel de Grote Hogeschool

The ALPHA Squad	Eriks Gerbreders	Belgium	Karel de Grote Hogeschool
	Mariano Fragiacomio	Argentina	The Blue Pulse
	Matias F	Belgium	ALGAE ALPHA Signals (AAS-AI)
	Richard Cardwell	Spain	TMS Maritime Solutions
	Limara Haque	United Kingdom	The Blue Pulse
	NIKOLAOS DIKAIOS	Greece	Academy of Athens
	Tom De Block	Belgium	The Blue Pulse
	Georgia Anastasini	Greece	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
	Laure Vancauwenberghe	Switzerland	Swiss Data Science Center
MusselAlert	Nadithi Tissera	Canada	University of Calgary
	Hossam Elshahaby	Sweden	ASU university
	ROXANI ARCHONTI	Greece	University of Thessaly
	Georgios Tzormpatzakis	Greece	University of Patras

Kraken the Code	Nikhil Garg	United States	San Jose State University
	Angeliki Kaskani	Greece	University of Patras
	Mohammad Shafiul Azam Khan	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
	Michael Wathen	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
	Emma Sullivan	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
	Jane Netting	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
	Molly James	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
	Benjamin O'Driscoll	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
	Peter Walker	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
	Tom Mansfield	United Kingdom	Plymouth Marine Laboratory
Pierluigi Di Pietro	Italy	ingv	

MedSea Investigators	Michael Warren Ceballos	Spain	Universidad Católica de Valencia San Vicente Martir (Spain)
	Damiano Delrosso	Italy	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV)
	Marjahn Finlayson	Italy	Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia
EcoSea EO	Ederson Enriquez	Ecuador	GIS4 Wildlife
	Bryan Vallejo	Ecuador	GIS4 Wildlife
	Tran Ngo	Viet Nam	VTT
Blume	Geannyra Cortez	Peru	-
	Raúl Galdeano Pazos	Spain	Cetaqua - Water Technology Center
	Alisson Fuentes	Peru	-
	Luis Alonzo Contreras Perez	Peru	-
	gabriel barrientos	Peru	-
	Natalia Falla Valdez	Peru	-

	Oscar Castro	Peru	-
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The pitches of the 10 finalist Teams can be found here:

- **TwinTrack** – DTO Meets Animal Movement: Mapping Marine Movements in the North Sea: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eq59lBJxbqrgsUTCep06533ZCE-yoly/view?usp=drive_link
- **Blue-Cloud Marine** – The Blue-Cloud Marine Early Warning System: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1wxWQZVJucBCAPPEX9nhFiO954FuicTwB/view?usp=drive_link
- **RugOBSS** – Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Xwj2Sn-wJxISq10nhzW-58AqoZTjCHPz/view?usp=drive_link
- **Smiley axolotl** – ParviFlo — where, when, and why the O may flip—before it does: https://drive.google.com/file/d/12UU8tTvov29Ovb61xZvKpOeltntw7Trp/view?usp=drive_link
- **The ALPHA Squad** – ALGAE ALPHA signals (AAS-AI): https://drive.google.com/file/d/1KUVx0g9svHF46nmMghS35wCrj8EE-ena/view?usp=drive_link
- **MusselAlert** – A Stress Risk Alert System for Mussel Farms: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1QY30-xbsf-0Xz3QY1tG8toOatYcfmFG/view?usp=drive_link
- **Kraken the Code** – OctoPulse: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1F88OleOxMUqwECVkuC8A3anRCZr3y4VY/view?usp=drive_link
- **MedSea Investigators** – Updating the Mediterranean Outflow Water (MOW) Indicator: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1D-8DI8j-p4e0Ftgxu26bhzEEzCbDAPxt/view?usp=drive_link
- **EcoSea EO** – EcoSea EO-Monitoring Eutrophication Impacts from Wastewater on Marine Environments: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1P5tF5cC_gQQ4o2moXpNICtYy7Kus8Ddp/view?usp=drive_link
- **Blume** – MarIA: An AI-Powered Predictive Model for Sustainable Fisheries: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1lydrhTiaJ0xm3yUOPTboTA4FzoFdSCTb/view?usp=drive_link

3.3. Winner Teams

The final 3 winners appointed by the event Jury were:

1. Team: TwinTrack – [DTO Meets Animal Movement: Mapping Movements in the North Sea](#)

- **Challenge: #2** — *Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents or Natural Events*
Blue-Cloud service leveraged: Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service and Virtual Research Environments, used to access harmonised biological and environmental datasets.
- **Description:** TwinTrack proposed a Digital Twin Ocean-ready workflow to integrate animal movement data with environmental datasets for the North Sea. Their approach supports improved ecosystem indicators, early-warning responses, and compliance tracking for EU marine directives.
- **Blue-Cloud service leveraged:** Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service. Used to identify, access and aggregate environmental layers and biological datasets needed to merge **animal movement trajectories** with Digital Twin Ocean-ready variables.

2. Team: Kraken the Code – [Monitoring invasive macroalgae through data-driven methods](#)

- **Challenge: #2** — *Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents or Natural Events*
Blue-Cloud service leveraged: Blue-Cloud VRE analytics tools, used to process biological datasets and derive automated detection outputs.
- **Description:** Kraken the Code developed OctoPulse, a data-driven approach that uses environmental variables and open datasets to improve the detection and monitoring of invasive macroalgae. The workflow enables earlier response, improves situational awareness, and reduces the workload for monitoring teams.
- **Blue-Cloud service leveraged:** Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) analytics tools. The team used VRE-type analytical workflows for predictive modelling, environmental correlation analysis and harmonised biological dataset processing

3. Team: RugOBSS – [Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System](#)

- **Challenge: #3** — *Sustainable Blue Economy Applications*
- **Blue-Cloud service leveraged:** Blue-Cloud data harmonisation services, integrating biological and coastal datasets for classification workflows.

- **Description:** RugOBSS addresses one of the Mediterranean’s growing concerns: beachcast invasive macroalgae. Their application proposes a streamlined monitoring system using a mix of local observations, historical data and automated classification to support coastal managers and restoration efforts.
- **Blue-Cloud service leveraged:** Blue-Cloud Data Harmonisation & Integration Services
 Their workflow relies on harmonised biological and coastal datasets, consistent metadata, and interoperable classifications — all supported by Blue-Cloud’s data access and standardisation services.

3.4. Usage of Blue-Cloud 2026 assets and resources

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) hosts all the assets that were to be tested during the hackathon. The event proved to be an excellent way of exposing the Blue-Cloud ecosystem of services to new users. During the event:

- 423 new users registered to the platform.
- More than 10,000 working sessions were registered.

The figure below provides an overview of the number of new sessions registered in each Virtual Lab during the hackathon days:

Date	2025-09	2025-10
Carbon Plankton Dynamics	209	79
Coastal Currents from Observations	559	291
Ecosystem-Workbench	381	3
Eutrophication-Workbench	60	25
Global Fisheries Atlas	392	119
ICOOE	578	140
Marine Environmental Indicators	664	378
Physics-Workbench	190	82

Figure 7: Sessions per Virtual Lab during the Blue-Cloud 2025 Hackathon

The traction of the hackathon can also be measured in terms of VRE sessions and computing resources used by participants during the event, amounting to:

- 4851 VRE sessions, vs 2114 average sessions executed over the last 12 months prior to the event.
- 214 cloud computing processes executed, exploiting each up to 8 CPUs and 32 GB RAM, vs 50 average over the last 12 months prior to the event.
- 1518 execution of notebooks and RStudio environment vs 340 notebooks and 133 RStudio average sessions over the last 12 months prior to the event.

Figure 8: Blue-Cloud VRE access, processes and notebooks executed

3.5. Participant feedback and survey

Post-event surveys indicated high satisfaction levels among participants. Respondents praised the clarity of the hackathon structure, the quality of mentoring, and the usefulness of Blue-Cloud tools. Many participants expressed interest in continued engagement with Blue-Cloud and EDITO through future hackathons or research collaborations.

For a detailed overview of the survey results, please see Section 5 (Annex: Full Visual Report).

Survey

Figure 9: Snapshot of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 Survey Results (see Section 5)

3.6. Feedback from Coaches & Mentors

As part of the evaluation of the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, the team of Coaches & Mentors was invited to provide reflections on their experience, the organisation of the event, the maturity and quality of the solutions developed, and suggestions for future editions. The feedback received highlights several common themes regarding platform usability, team engagement, resource suitability, duration, and evaluation procedures. Overall, the feedback was very positive, highlighting the usefulness of the event to test and progress the services being deployed in the Blue-Cloud VRE, in spite of the time that had to be invested to support the preparation of materials and presentations.

“It was a pleasure to participate in the Hackathon, and I truly appreciated the organisation and the experience.” Rafael Gomes de Mendoza (Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 Mentor)

The main challenges/areas for improvement identified by Coaches & Mentors include:

- Participants were exposed to a very broad portfolio of resources, and in spite of the 2-week warm up phase, had limited time to explore the full portfolio.

- In spite of the high number of registrations, there were teams that hardly reached out to their assigned Mentor requesting support.
- Some of the solutions put forward by the participating Teams were hard to assess, since they provided their outputs in various formats, some of which were not easy to re-run. Also, they seemed to be quite theoretical, without providing a real “proof of concept”, which made it difficult to assess them.
- Several of the projects that reached the top 10 entered the hackathon as already-established teams with elements of their ideas partially developed beforehand. This created an imbalance for the teams that were formed during the event and had to build their projects entirely from scratch, as it was difficult for newly formed groups to reach a comparable level of maturity within the timeline of the event.
- One Lead Mentor considered that the time allocated to evaluate the solutions delivered by assigned teams was insufficient to inspect all deliverables and evaluate them in depth.

The main **recommendations** put forward by Coaches & Mentors for future hackathons include:

- Reduce the scope of resources that are made available to participants, concentrating on the more mature assets, and adapt the challenges to focus on these.
- Consider creating different competition categories, i.e., 1) for teams entering with pre-existing or partially developed projects, and 2) for newly formed teams that start during the hackathon. This could help ensure a fairer competition while giving proper space and visibility to both types of participants.
- Extend the hackathon time to 1 week, instead of 2.5 days, with support over shorter, pre-defined time slots (to avoid increasing the workload for Coaches & Mentors), providing participants with more time to work on their ideas and deliverables.
- Make it compulsory for all participating teams to provide as one of the requested outputs and as part of their solution a proof of concept that is backed by code in a pre-defined format (ideally an HTML file). This would allow for a quick assessment on veracity and interest.
- Allow more time for the evaluation of the Teams’ deliverables.

4. Conclusions

The Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 marked a major milestone for the HE Blue-Cloud 2026 project, demonstrating the value and versatility of its federated open science environment for ocean and aquatic research. By mobilising over a thousand participants from diverse disciplines and geographies, the hackathon successfully showcased the potential of co-creation and cross-sector collaboration in accelerating marine data innovation.

The event validated key core services and thematic assets deployed by the Blue-Cloud 2026 project — namely its Virtual Labs and Workbenches — as powerful enablers for innovative development of solutions to address ocean challenges. The engagement of over 30 mentors and coaches from the Blue-Cloud 2026 project Consortium and from the EDITO communities significantly enhanced participants' capacity to ideate, develop, and deliver meaningful prototypes in a short time frame.

The use of real marine datasets, combined with guided access to digital twin infrastructure and cloud-based computing environments, empowered teams to address pressing marine challenges in new ways — from tracking biodiversity and monitoring invasive species to developing early warning systems and improving ocean health forecasting.

The positive feedback collected from participants, alongside the quality of the final project submissions, confirmed the relevance of the services deployed by the Blue-Cloud 2026 project in supporting the next generation of marine data practitioners and innovators. The event also provided the consortium with important user insights to further refine and evolve its tools and workflows in line with real-world needs and marked another step forward in aligning developments with EDITO, the public infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean.

Looking ahead, the hackathon's outcomes will feed into future stakeholder engagement and training activities under Blue-Cloud 2026 and support the wider European objectives of fostering a FAIR, open, and federated research ecosystem. The success of this edition reinforces the value of hackathons as a strategic format for advancing marine science, policy, and innovation in the digital age.

5. Annex: Full Visual Report

Blue-Cloud2026

A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem
for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Hackathon Days
29 Sep - 2 Oct 2025

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Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

BLUE-CLOUD HACKATHON 2025 FINAL REPORT

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Blue-Cloud2026

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for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters

About

The Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 (**29 Sept - 2 Oct**) was a collaborative event inviting scientists, researchers, and innovators to **explore** the **open science ecosystem** developed by the Blue-Cloud pilot and Blue-Cloud 2026 projects.

It gave participants the chance to **test** and **design data-driven workflows** using the platform's **Virtual Labs, Workbenches, and analytical tools** to extract insights from marine data and solve specific ocean related knowledge challenges.

Challenge 1 - Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystems and Species

How might we use collaborative science to advance the knowledge of marine ecosystems and species? Marine ecosystems and their diverse species play a vital role in our lives. They regulate the Earth's...

Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents or Natural Events

How might we use collaborative science to advance our ability to predict risks from natural events, or to ensure a swift response to accidents at sea? Global change is affecting the way that oceans fe...

Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health

How might we use environmental indicators to understand complex phenomena affecting marine ecosystems and detect changes in their status with sufficient time to respond? Climate change is causing sever...

Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!

How might we leverage the European Digital Twin Ocean platform to address Ocean challenges? EDITO is the public backbone infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean. This wildcard invites you to...

- Registrations and team formation open
13 May @ 14:00
- Virtual warm up starts!
16 September @ 15:00
- Virtual warm up ends!
25 September @ 15:00
- ✗ Registration and team formation close and Idea description submission
26 September @ 12:00
- Hackathon starts
29 September @ 10:00
- Deliverable 1
29 September @ 16:00
- Deliverable 2
30 September @ 14:00
- Deliverable 3
30 September @ 10:00
- Deliverable 4 [OPTIONAL]
1 October @ 11:00
- Deliverable 5 // Video Pitch
1 October @ 13:00
- Evaluation process starts
1 October @ 13:01
- Pitching and winners announcement!
2 October @ 15:00

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

CHALLENGES

Challenge 1 - Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystems and Species

How might we use collaborative science to advance the knowledge of marine ecosystems and species?

Marine ecosystems and their diverse species play a vital role in our lives. They regulate the Earth's climate and are a primary source of food for billions of people. They support numerous economic activities and provide livelihoods for coastal communities around the World. However, from plankton -the fabric of the Ocean-, to fisheries, our knowledge of species and ecosystems remains difficult to analyze with integrative approaches. With your help, we can hack available data to address important knowledge gaps.

How could you tackle this challenge? Here are some ideas for inspiration. Using the resources provided across the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (including those available in VLab "Plankton Genomics", VLab "Global Fisheries Atlas" and in the "Ecosystem-level Essential Ocean Variables Workbench" VLab):

- Map the geographical distribution of important genomic pathways within small planktonic organisms from genomic data.
- Map the geographical distribution of key life history traits of planktonic organisms, accessible from imaging data.
- Overlay planktonic organism data with fisheries data on a particular area (e.g. a water area) and compare their time-dependent data (e.g. increases in phytoplankton or zooplankton precede increases in the corresponding stocks in these areas).

Resources from a minimum of 2 V Labs or Workbenches should be used for all solutions.

All solutions should utilise Blue-Cloud services or resources (including in combination with other open data).

Challenge 1 - Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystems and Species

How might we use collaborative science to advance the knowledge of marine ecosystems and species? Marine ecosystems and their diverse species play a vital role in our lives. They regulate the Earth's climate.

Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents or Natural Events

How might we use collaborative science to advance our ability to predict risks from natural events, or to ensure a swift response to accidents at sea?

Global change is affecting the way that species feed, move, and inhabit the marine realm. Species migrations can have an impact on human livelihoods that rely on fisheries as a source of protein for human consumption. In addition, activities at sea carry risks to human life, and to wildlife. With your help, we can evolve early warning mechanisms to anticipate a more effective response to global change.

How could you tackle this challenge? Here are some ideas for inspiration. Using the resources provided across the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (but specially those available in the Virtual Lab "Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe"):

- Suggest solutions to assess the impact of invasive species on offshore aquaculture farms.
- Suggest solutions to assess the impact of oil spills on Marine Protected Areas and on the coast.
- Suggest solutions to assess the impact of extreme events on offshore aquaculture farms.
- Propose solutions to further understand regional circulation and changes (with impacts on marine ecosystems) using glider derived ocean indicators.

Resources from a minimum of 2 V Labs or Workbenches should be used for all solutions.

All solutions should utilise Blue-Cloud services or resources (including in combination with other open data).

Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health

How might we use environmental indicators to understand complex phenomena affecting marine ecosystems and detect changes in their status with sufficient time to respond?

Climate change is causing severe impacts on marine ecosystems. However, these changes are often difficult to anticipate, leading to delays in the implementation of actions that could mitigate risks and help us adapt to new conditions. With your help, we can track and anticipate changes in the health of marine ecosystems to anticipate a more effective response.

How could you tackle this challenge? Here are some ideas for inspiration. Using the resources provided across the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (but specially those available in the Virtual Labs "Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe", "Ocean Currents from Observations" and "Marine Environmental Indicators"):

- Suggest solutions to making predictions about the dispersion of different pollution scenarios (e.g., in the Mediterranean Sea), using a Lagrangian drifter model. The drifter model will need to be implemented to predict drifter trajectories based on surface currents data products available, and based on different scenarios of initial positions. Pollution can be considered to be a passive tracer for this challenge.
- Suggest solutions to better understanding and tracking thermal trends, getting insight on the way heat storage influences marine ecosystem structure and function over time.
- Suggest solutions to identify where potential eutrophication hotspots might occur in the Mediterranean sea using the spatial variation in the eutrophication indicator (TRIX), and relating these hotspots to possible major contributing factors.
- Suggest solutions to better understanding ocean warming patterns and trends in different regions and layers of the Mediterranean Sea, harnessing different data sources. Are current estimates consistent? Which regions or layers of the Mediterranean Sea are warming more rapidly?

Resources from a minimum of 2 V Labs or Workbenches should be used for all solutions.

All solutions should utilise Blue-Cloud services or resources (including in combination with other open data).

Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!

How might we leverage the European Digital Twin Ocean platform to address Ocean challenges?

EDITO is the public backbone infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean. This wildcard invites you to address any Ocean challenge of your choice, harnessing the resources available in the EDITO platform in combination with resources offered by Blue-Cloud.

How could you tackle this challenge? The sky's the limit! Explore EDITO Data Lake, bringing you Copernicus Marine and EMODnet data, or dive into the wealth of community resources available on the EDITO platform -from applications to "what-if" scenarios-, and find creative ways of combining them with the services that are available within the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment to advance marine knowledge.

Resources from a minimum of 2 VLabs or Workbenches should be used for all solutions.

All solutions should utilise Blue-Cloud services or resources (including in combination with other open data).

Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!

How might we leverage the European Digital Twin Ocean platform to address Ocean challenges? EDITO is the public backbone infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean. This wildcard invites you to

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

HACKATHON PARTNERS

Hackathon partners

The Blue-Cloud 2026 project is powered by open marine data & resources from:

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN

Meta campaign key figures

Reach - 463k
Impressions - 1.6 mio
Frequency - 3.45
Page views - 8k
Clicks on "Register" button - 1.8k
Cost per click - €0.14
Click through rate - 1.10%

Pristine Agency
Sponsored · 🌐

- 📍 Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025
- 👤 Welcoming multidisciplinary talents
- 📅 29 September - 2 October 2025
- 🏆 Win and Pitch at the Blue-Cloud Final Event!
- 📝 Register today!

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Hackathon Days
29 Sep - 2 Oct 2025
REGISTER TILL 26 SEPTEMBER

hackathon2025.blue-cloud.org
Shape ocean futures at Blue-Cloud 2025! **Sign up**

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REGISTER TILL 26 SEPTEMBER

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Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025 ...more

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Direct emailing campaign

- Direct emails sent: 15k
- Faculties:
 - Marine Science
 - Oceanography
 - Earth Sciences
 - Geology
 - Biosciences
 - Environmental sciences
 - Space
- GEO: Europe & North America
- Target audience: PhDs, Researchers, Students, Professors
- Contacted entities: 290

- Direct invites to participate in the BCH: 1619
- Events
 - OSL 3.0
 - OSL 4.0
 - WEKEO hackathon 2023
 - Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2022
 - Ocean4Biotech Hackathon

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

LANDING PAGES ANALYTICS

<https://hackathon2025.blue-cloud.org/>

Click here for the full report

Email michele@pristineagency.eu for full GA4 access.

<https://hackathon2025.blue-cloud.org/>

Active users™ by Country

COUNTRY	ACTIVE USERS
United States	689
India	613
United Kingdom	566
Germany	371
Peru	370
Brazil	333
Greece	321

Active users™ by Gender

Click here for the full report

Active users™ by Interests

INTERESTS	ACTIVE USERS
Technology/Technop...	491
Lifestyles & Hobbies...	332
News & Politics/Avid...	233
Travel/Travel Buffs	221
News & Politics/Avid...	200
Sports & Fitness/Sp...	176
Technology/Social M...	176

Active users™ by Age

Active users™ by Language

Reports

Email michele@pristineagency.eu for full GA4 access.

<https://eventornado.com/event/blue-cloud-hackathon-2025#home>

Click here for the full report

Email michele@pristineagency.eu for full GA4 access.

<https://eventornado.com/event/blue-cloud-hackathon-2025#home>

Active users* by Country

COUNTRY	ACTIVE USERS
India	387
United Kingdom	227
United States	181
Peru	154
Greece	124
Italy	110
Spain	103

Active users* by Gender

■ FEMALE 50.5%
 ■ MALE 49.5%

Click here for the full report

Reports

Active users* by Interests

INTERESTS	ACTIVE USERS
Technology/Technop...	193
Lifestyles & Hobbies...	124
News & Politics/Avid...	85
Travel/Travel Buffs	85
Technology/Social M...	66
Lifestyles & Hobbies...	64
News & Politics/Avid...	61

Active users* by Age

Active users* by Language

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REGISTRATION AND TEAMS' DATA

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Registration data

Teams registered: 118
 Participants registered: 1140

Eligible teams: 70
 Teams per challenge:

- 1 - 21 teams
- 2 - 25 teams
- 3 - 19 teams
- 4 - 5 teams

Participants in eligible teams: 348

Teams who submitted all deliverables: 22
 Participants of the above teams: 131

Registrants

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PARTICIPATING TEAMS

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Challenge 1

Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystems and Species

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Blume

MarIA: An AI-Powered Predictive Model for Sustainable Fisheries

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Oscar Castro

Natalia Falla Valdez

Gabriel Barrientos

Luis Alonzo Contreras Perez

Alisson Fuentes

Geannyra Cortez

Raúl Galdeano Pazos

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DeepZee

An interactive site shows the distribution of marine species

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Micky C

Maria Celestina Henriques
Kalina Dimitrova
Wiktorja Michalska

Dmitriy K

Ian Woodworth
Foteini Iatrou
Konstantinos Kavakakis

THE DEEPZEE

!! This is just a prototype
Not the final version

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Challenge 2

Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents or Natural Events

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

The ALPHA squad ALGAE ALPHA Signals (AAS-AI)

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Tom De Block
Nikolaos Dikaios
Limara Haque
Matias F
Mariano Fragiacomò

Georgia Anastasini
Nadithi Tissera
Laure Vancauwenberghe
Richard Cardwell

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PhytoNET

PhytoNet: An AI-Powered Early-Warning System for Sustainable Marine Livelihoods

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Devakrishnan Krishnakumar
Prabhupada Satpathy

Vaishnav Suraj
Pragateeshwaran Saravanan

Current HAB systems are like looking in the rearview mirror

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

RugOBSS Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Mar Roca Mora
Bede Ffinian Rowe Davies
Maria João Borlido Oliveira Lima

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Kraken the code
OctoPulse

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Tom Mansfield
Jane Netting
Benjamin O'Driscoll
Emma Sullivan

Molly James
Peter Walker
Michael Wathen
Mohammad Shafiul Azan Khan

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

DELIVERABLE 5

OctoPulse Video Pitch

brought to you by *Kraken The Code*
V1.0 | 1st Oct. 2025

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Blue-Cloud Marine The Blue-Cloud Marine Early Warning System

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Michael Inso
Maria Arredondo
Laura Ballesteros

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Hello everyone

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Jelly Guard Team

Jelly Guard – Smart Jellyfish Alert System for Early Warning and Marine Safety

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Leonardo Tronci
Tiziana Mori
Massimiliano Tronci

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Challenge 3

Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

MareSyn - 1

Tracking and Forecasting Eutrophication and Hypoxia in European Seas

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Rafiqul Alam Intiaj
Saif Mehjabin
Mohammad Borhan Uddin
Nazrul Islam Rakib

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

EcoSea EO

EcoSea EO Monitoring Eutrophication Impacts from Wastewater on Marine
Environments

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Bryan Vallejo
Tran Ngo
Ederson Enriquez

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Smiley axolotl

Parviflo — where, when, and why the O may flip—before it does

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Daniil Mumladze
Eriks Gerbreders
Eva Reichel
Alina Dimova

Qosai Abu Ahmed
Alec Tuffin
Martyna Hajduk

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Calypso
SeaNet

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Albert Schwanzer
Michal Branda
Kristýna Říhová
David Nohejl

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ThermoStatus
Tracker of Marine Heat Waves in the Western Black Sea

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Douglas Silva

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Source water type matrix contributor = observational data + residuals

$$T_1 X_1 + T_2 X_2 + T_3 X_3 \dots = \text{observational data} + \text{residuals}$$

$$S_1 X_1 + S_2 X_2 + S_3 X_3 \dots = \text{observational data} + \text{residuals}$$

$$X_1 + X_2 + X_3 \dots = 1 + \text{residuals}$$

3D structure of the water mass

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Water Tribe
Lugia

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Aaryaman Saini
Pulkit Agarwal
Ujjawal Aggarwal

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Challenge 4

Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

CoastBusters
Baltic Coast Twin

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Aleksandra Dudkowska
Armin Halicki
Gabriela Gic-Grusza
Adrian Bugaj

Idea name:
Baltic Coast Twin

Challenge Category:
Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Ingenium
IMENSA Blue Nutriscore

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Demetrio Alessandro Trunfio
Ferdinando Potenza
Anna Mezzapesa
Antonio Andrea Tondi

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MusselAlert

MusselAlert: A Stress Risk Alert System for Mussel Farms

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Angeliki Kaskani
Nikhil Garg
Georgios Tzormpatzakis

Roxani Archonti
Hossam Elshahaby

Team Mussel Alert

Early Warning System for Mediterranean Mussel Farms

TEAM LEADER
ANGELIKI
KASKANI

TEAM MEMBER
NIKHIL GARG

TEAM MEMBER
GEORGIOS
TZORMPATZAKIS

TEAM MEMBER
ROXANI
ARCHONTI

TEAM
MEMBER
HOSSAM
ELSHAHABY

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

essiHack

From Ocean Data to Meaning - Dive, Connect, and Comprehend

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Riccardo Maetzke
Ahmad Mahmoud
Enrico Boldrini

Massimiliano Olivieri
Fabrizio Papeschi

Istituto sull'Inquinamento Atmosferico
Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
FIRENZE

essiHack

CNR-IIA

From Ocean Data to Meaning - Dive, Connect, and Comprehend

The essiHack team:

Riccardo Maetzke (team leader, CNR-IIA research fellow)

Ahmad Mahmoud (developer, CNR-IIA/UNIFI intern)

**Massimiliano Olivieri (technical collaborator, CNR-IIA
technician)**

Fabrizio Papeschi (developer, CNR-IIA technician)

Enrico Boldrini (coach, CNR-IIA researcher)

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

TwinTrack

DTO Meets Animal Movement: Mapping Marine Movements in the North Sea

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Lotte Pohl

Ahmad Widyatmoko

Natalie Klinard

Chris Monk

Samuel Fooks

Ross McGill

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MedSea Investigators

Updating the Mediterranean Outflow Water (MOW) Indicator through a workflow study using multiple data sources

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Marjahn Finlayson
Damiano Delrosso

Pierluigi Di Pietro
Michael Warren Ceballos

A Report By The MedSea Investigators

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

SkadiX

SkadiX - Mapping Ports Suitability for Cold-Chain Logistics in Europe

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Dhimas Upadyandaru
Arief Ihsan Widhanto
Muhammad Ridwan Ramadhan
Suhendra Anang Prasetyo

David Cotter
Ciaran Griffin
Emilia Curyło
Andreya Paiva

Blue-Cloud
Hackathon 20

Dimas Upadyandaru

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Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Nautilus

Fine Tuning a Sea Drone for Environmental Impact Assessment and Search and Rescue Missions

[LINK TO DELIVERABLES](#)

Fotis Zapantis

Hideo Riz'n

Dolapo Salim Olatoye

Bence Hernádi

Nandini Gantayat

Mélinda Martins

Nicholas Tsen

John Karagiorgos

Overview

Navigation and Orientation
Power and Propulsion
Safety and Rescue Features
Operational Highlights

Applications

Flood Rescue Operations
WaterWay Patrols
Disaster Relief and Evacuation
Swift water rescue in sea, rivers
and lakes

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

LIVE SESSIONS

Live session 1 - Welcome! Blue-Cloud Essentials

Unique viewers: 101
Q&As: 12

This live session aimed to welcome participants, introduce the Blue-Cloud Hackathon journey, and provide essential context, tools, and inspiration to kick off the virtual ideation warm-up.

In this live session, we explored ocean-related challenges, introduced the Blue-Cloud 2026 project and its Virtual Research Environment (VRE), learned about Ocean Best Practices, and received guidance on how to join even without a specific idea!

The slide features a dark blue background with a glowing blue particle trail forming a circular shape. At the top, the text "Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025" is displayed in large white font. Below this, a semi-transparent blue box contains the text "Live Session 1 Welcome! Blue-Cloud Essentials" in white. At the bottom left, there is a logo for the European Union with the text "Funded by the European Union". At the bottom right, the "eosc | Blue-Cloud 2026" logo is visible.

Live Session 2 - On Blue-Cloud's Services: Explore the Virtual Labs!

Unique viewers: 63
Q&As: 4

This live session introduced the five thematic Virtual Labs, providing participants with the opportunity to ask questions directly to the VLab coaches.

Blue-Cloud
Hackathon 2025

Live Session 2
On Blue-Cloud's Services:
Explore The Virtual Labs!

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The banner features a dark blue background with a glowing blue particle trail. The text is white and centered. At the bottom, there are logos for the European Union and the event itself.

Live Session 3 - On Blue-Cloud's Services: Explore the Workbenches, Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service, and Beacon!

Unique viewers: 62
Q&As: 8

This live session provided a hands-on introduction to key tools and platforms available for the hackathon. Experts explained the EOV Workbenches for Eutrophication, Physics, and Ecosystems, followed by demos of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service, Beacon, and webODV.

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Live Session 3
On Blue-Cloud's Services: Explore The
Workbenches, Blue-Cloud Data Discovery &
Access Service, And Beacon!

Blue-Cloud Hackathon - Live Session 4 - Get familiar with the Hackathon Challenges!

Unique viewers: 53
Q&As: 1

This live session introduced the four main hackathon challenges in detail, helping participants choose the one that best aligns with their interests and skills. Each challenge leader presented the focus area, objectives, and relevant data/tools.

The slide features a dark blue background with a light blue gradient and a subtle pattern of white dots. The main title 'Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025' is at the top left in large white font. Below it, a semi-transparent blue box contains the text 'Live Session 4' and 'Get Familiar With The Hackathon Challenges!' in white. At the bottom left is the European Union logo and 'Funded by the European Union'. At the bottom right is the 'eosc | Blue-Cloud 2025' logo.

Hackathon Kick-Off

Unique viewers: 64

Poll	Responses
Poll 1	35
Poll 2	28
Poll 3	33
Poll 4	33
Poll 5	35
Poll 6	35
Poll 7	43

The Blue-Cloud Hackathon Pitching & Award Ceremony!

Unique viewers: 80
Q&As: 8

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

COACHES, MENTORS & JURY MEMBERS

Jury Members

Elisa Ravagnan
NORCE

Marco Filippone
Fugro

Dave Mills
Bangor University

Mary Malicet
Mercator Ocean International

Othman Cherkaoui Dekkaki
ECOP Morocco Steering Committee

Name	Role	Organisation/Work title
Cyrielle Delvenne	Challenge Leader	Marine Project & Data Manager - Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
Jean-Olivier Irisson	Challenge Leader	Associate professor at Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Julia Vera	Challenge Leader	Lead Manager Business & Strategy at Seascope Belgium
Simona Simoncelli	Challenge Leader	Researcher at INGV
Bastien Grasset	Coach	Fisheries Research engineer at IRD (French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development)
Enrico Baglione	Coach	Researcher at INGV
Francesco Palermo	Coach	Senior Research Assistant at the CMCC Foundation
Juan Gabriel Fernández Pineda	Coach	Head of Data Center and Software Developer at SOCIB
Marco Lettere	Coach	Chair and CTO at Nubisware
Mauro Mugnaini	Coach	Nubisware S.r.l
Nydia Catalina Reyes Suarez	Coach	Research Technologist at the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
Paul Weerheim	Coach	Software Developer at Maris
Robin Kooyman	Coach	Software Developer at Maris
Sebastian Mieruch	Coach	Researcher, Software Developer at Alfred Wegener Institute
Vânia Lima	Coach	Researcher, Software Developer at Instituto Hidrografico (IH)
Victoria Bancel	Coach	Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Alexandre Schickele	Coach + Mentor	Postdoctoral researcher at ETH Zürich
Felix Dols	Coach + Mentor	Civil engineer at Deltares
Rafael Gomes de Menezes	Coach + Mentor	Research Assistant at CMCC
Joao Vitorino	Mentor	Oceanographer at Instituto Hidrografico (IH)
Josephine Broussin	Mentor	Postdoc at ETHZ
Matteo Bazzaro	Mentor	Permanent Researcher at the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
Megan Anne French	Mentor	Researcher at National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS
Merlin Weiss	Mentor	PhD Student at ETH Zurich
Salvatore Causio	Mentor	Senior Researcher at CMCC
Sarah Hasnain	Mentor	Post-doctoral researcher at Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Virginie Sonnet	Mentor	Post-doctoral researcher at Sorbonne Université (SU) - Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV)
Abel Dechenne	Mentor + Coach	PhD Candidate at the University of Liège
Alexander Barth	Mentor + Coach	Associate Professor at the University of Liège
Julien Barde	Mentor + Coach	IT research engineer at IRD (French National Research Institute for Sustainable Development)

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

PRIZE POOL

Prize pool

Winners will pitch their ideas at the Blue-Cloud Final Conference & gain exclusive access to the EDITO platform.

- The top 3 teams received up to €25,000 in total financial support to further develop and promote their solutions, with guidance from the Blue-Cloud 2026 project.
- Travel expenses covered for the winners to participate in Blue-Cloud 2026 events, including its Final Conference.
- Winners will gain exclusive access to the EDITO platform.

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

MINI CHALLENGES

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Mini Challenge 1 Data in a picture

Capture a **screenshot, graph or map** from the Blue-Cloud 2026 platform that amazes you and share it with a one-sentence explanation.

#BlueCloudHackathon

Mini Challenge 2 Ocean pledge

Share a **personal action** you'll take to protect the ocean, inspired by something you discovered in Blue-Cloud data.

#BlueCloudHackathon

Mini challenges

[LINK TO ALL MINI CHALLENGES](#)

Suhendra Anang P. · 3rd · [@suhendraanangp](#) · Follow

My "Ocean Pledge" for the #BlueCloudStackathon is inspired by a stark reality I saw in the data while building our #stackit project: food waste on land is directly connected to ocean health. A fully cold chain for seafood means we waste fish, energy, and put needless strain on marine ecosystems. So, my pledge is to champion data-driven logistics. By building smarter, we can reduce waste and better protect our vital ocean resources. Let's make every catch count. #BlueCloud2024

John Decker · 2nd · [@johndecker](#) · Follow

The #stackit project is a great example of the #BlueCloudStackathon, for building the #stackit project.

- These fish always come out of the North Sea coast.
- The shipping route is not optimal for the fish, but it is a good example of the #BlueCloudStackathon.

Stack it up with #BlueCloud2024. Let's make every catch count.

Yaita Sumeragi · 4th · [@mikaelioinotech](#)

Ready for the Mini Challenge? - Ocean Pledge! From Blue-Cloud data I've learned how fragile marine ecosystems are - so I pledge to cut single-use plastics and support sustainable seafood choices.

#BlueCloudStackathon @BlueCloudEU

Ocean Pledge

[@BlueCloudStackathon](#) [@BlueCloudEU](#)

X · 10/29/2024 1:32 PM

THE PROBLEM: A VISCIOUS CYCLE

THE SOLUTION: DATA-DRIVEN PORT

TECH + PORTS = A RESILIENT PLASTIC-FREE BLUE ECONOMY

Leonardo · 1st · [@leonardof](#) · Follow

Together with my teammates, I'm applying Blue-Cloud's Marine Environmental Intelligence to help us...

- "Marine" - key parameters affecting fish health
- "Intelligence" - specific analysis on the fish's environment
- "Marine" - fish health (climate change)

The data we're processing will power our early warning system to protect coastal areas and marine ecosystems. 🌊

👉 "How great?" Creating sustainable technology that combines data science and artificial intelligence for ocean conservation.

👉 "Please join your team!" at the #BlueCloudStackathon and share your ideas and suggestions with us!

Blue-Cloud interface showing a map of Europe and various data points.

Blue-Cloud interface showing a map of Europe and various data points.

ed by European Uni

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Mini challenge winners

Mini challenge 1
Data in a picture

Jelly Guard Team

Funded by
the European Union

Leonardo Tronci · 3rd+
Studente presso Liceo Classico Europeo Convitto Cagliari, ITALY
2d · Edited · 🌐

🔥 ****Team JellyFish in action on Blue-Cloud!**** 🗨️
Mini Challenge n.1- Data in a Picture!

Together with my teammates, I'm exploring Blue-Cloud's Marine Environmental Indicators Virtual Lab to:

- 🔍 ****Identify**** key parameters affecting jellyfish blooms
- ⚙️ ****Configure**** specific analyses on the Italian Mediterranean
- 🗺️ ****Generate**** real-time climate maps

The data we're processing will power our early-warning robotic system to protect coastal areas and marine ecosystems. 🙌

🎯 ****Our goal?*** Creating sustainable technology that combines data science and robotic engineering for ocean conservation. 🌐

👉 ****Follow our journey**** in this #BlueCloudHackathon and share your ideas and suggestions with us! 📌

#JellyFishTeam #OceanTech #SustainableInnovation #MarineScience #DataDriven #Mediterranean #BlueCloudHackathon Blue-Cloud 2026

Navigation menu with a logo featuring a globe and waves.

- Home
- Parameters
- Configuration
- Real-time maps
- Help

Parameter	Value	Unit	Scale	Color	Map	Legend	Help
Sea Surface Temperature	20.0	°C	0-30	Blue	📍	📄	📖
Sea Surface Salinity	35.0	PSU	30-40	Green	📍	📄	📖
Sea Level Pressure	1013.0	hPa	990-1030	Red	📍	📄	📖
Sea Level Anomaly	0.0	m	-0.5-0.5	Yellow	📍	📄	📖
Sea Level Rise	0.0	m	-0.5-0.5	Orange	📍	📄	📖

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Mini challenges winner

Mini challenge 2
Ocean pledge

DeepZee

Funded by
the European Union

 Wiktoria Michalska • 3rd+
data analyst | student at Rome Business School | 🇵🇱 🇪🇺 |
2d • 🌐

🏆 mini challenge 🇪🇺! - Ocean pledge

🌊 As a member of the DeepZee team during Blue Cloud Hackathon 2025 and an open water diver, I take the ocean pledge 🌊:

As explorers above and below the surface, we pledge to protect and respect the ocean — our planet's life source.

Through

- 🔬 science,
- 🚀 technology,
- 🤿 and first-hand experience as divers, we commit to making marine biodiversity visible, accessible, and understood.

🙌 By sharing knowledge on species, habitats, and climate impacts, we aim to empower others to care, act, and safeguard the ocean for future generations.

Blue-Cloud 2026

#bluecloudhackathon

PS. Yep, that's me in 2018 diving in the Pacific near The Big Island (Hawaii)

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

PRE-EVALUATION RESULTS

Pre-evaluation results - selecting the best 10 teams

The detailed evaluation results and scores can be found on [this file](#)

blue-cloud-hackathon-2025-reviews-20251001_135316

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A1	Team Name	Idea Title	Topic	Taj	Avg all	Weighted Avg all	Sum al	Your overall score	Sum all w/Bonus-Pen	Sum all rounds	Awar
1	Kraken the code	OctoPulse	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
2	TwinTrack	DTO Meets Animal Movement: Mapping Marine Movements in the Nor	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5
3	RugOBSS	Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5	9.5
4	Blue-Cloud Marine	The Blue-Cloud Marine Early Warning System	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents	9	9	9	9	9	9	9	9
5	Blume	Maria: An AI-Powered Predictive Model for Sustainable Fisheries	Challenge 1 - Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystems and	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
6	The ALPHA squad	ALGAE ALPHA Signals (AAS-AI)	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5	8.5
7	EcoSea EO	EcoSea EO	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
8	MuselAlert	MuselAlert: A Stress Risk Alert System for Mussel Farms	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5	7.5
9	Smiley axolotl	Parviflo — where, when, and why the O may flip—before it does	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
10	MedSea Investigators	Updating the Mediterranean Outflow Water (MOW) Indicator through	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7
11	CoastBusters	Baltic Coast Twin	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
12	essiHack	From Ocean Data to Meaning - Dive, Connect, and Comprehend	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5
13	Calypto	SeaNet	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5	5.5
14	Jelly Guard Team	Jelly Guard – Smart Jellyfish Alert System for Early Warning and Marine	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
15	DeepZee	An interactive site shows the distribution of marine species	Challenge 1 - Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystems and	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
16	PhytoNET	PhytoNet: An AI-Powered Early-Warning System for Sustainable Marine	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Accidents	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
17	SkadIX	SkadIX - Mapping Ports Suitability for Cold-Chain Logistics in Europe	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5	4.5
18	Water Tribe	Lugia	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
19	ThermoStatus	Tracker of Marine Heat Waves in the Western Black Sea	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5	3.5
20	Ingenium	IMENSA Blue Nutriscore	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
21	MareSyn - 1	Tracking and Forecasting Eutrophication and Hypoxia in European Seas	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
22	Nautilus	Fine Tuning a Sea Drone for Environmental Impact Assessment and Sea	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

HACKATHON FINALISTS

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Finalist teams

MusselAlert

Challenge 4

MusselAlert: A Stress Risk Alert System for Mussel Farms

The ALPHA

squad

Challenge 2

ALGAE ALPHA Signals (AAS-AI)

TwinTrack

Challenge 4

DTO Meets Animal Movement: Mapping Marine Movements in the North Sea

Smiley axolotl

Challenge 3

Parviflo — where, when, and why the O may flip—before it does

RugOBSS

Challenge 2

Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System

Kraken the code

Challenge 2

OctoPulse

MedSea Investigators

Challenge 4

Updating the Mediterranean Outflow Water (MOW) Indicator

Blue-Cloud Marine

Challenge 2

The Blue-Cloud Marine Early Warning System

EcoSea EO

Challenge 3

EcoSea EO-Monitoring Eutrophication Impacts from Wastewater on Marine Environments

Blume

Challenge 1

MarIA: An AI-Powered Predictive Model for Sustainable Fisheries

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

EVALUATION RESULTS

Evaluation results - selecting the winners

The detailed evaluation results and scores can be found on [this file](#)

blue-cloud-hackathon-2025-reviews-20251008_161128

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A1	Team Name	Idea Title	Topic	Tag	Avg all	Weighted Avg all	Sum all	Fitness-for-purpose	Use of data
1	TwinTrack	DTO Meets Animal Movement: Mapping Marine Movements in the North Sea	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!		10.51428571	10.51428571	73.6		9.2
3	Kraken the code	OctoPulse	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Acci		9.714285714	9.714285714	68		9
4	RugOBSS	Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Acci		9.457142857	9.457142857	66.2		9.4
5	EcoSea EO	EcoSea EO	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health		8.857142857	8.857142857	62		8.8
6	Smiley axolotl	Parviflo — where, when, and why the O may flip—before it does	Challenge 3 - Tracking & Forecasting Ocean Health		8.657142857	8.657142857	60.6		7.6
7	The ALPHA squad	ALGAE ALPHA Signals (AAS-AJ)	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Acci		8.885714286	8.885714286	62.2		8.4
8	MedSea Investigators	Updating the Mediterranean Outflow Water (MOW) Indicator through a workflow study using	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!		8.485714286	8.485714286	59.4		8.6
9	Blue-Cloud Marine	The Blue-Cloud Marine Early Warning System	Challenge 2 - Supporting Early Warning & Response to Acci		8.514285714	8.514285714	59.6		8.8
10	Blume	MariaC: An AI-Powered Predictive Model for Sustainable Fisheries	Challenge 1 - Mapping & Understanding Marine Ecosystem		8.542857143	8.542857143	59.8		8.6
11	MusselAlert	MusselAlert: A Stress Risk Alert System for Mussel Farms	Challenge 4 - Wild Card: Double up with EDITO!		7.371428571	7.371428571	51.6		8.2

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

HACKATHON WINNERS

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Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

TwinTrack

DTO Meets Animal Movement: Mapping Marine Movements in the North Sea

Lotte Pohl

Ahmad Widyatmoko

Natalie Klinard

Chris Monk

Samuel Fooks

Ross McGill

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the European Union

eosc

Blue-Cloud2026

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for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

Kraken the code
OctoPulse

Tom Mansfield
Jane Netting
Benjamin O'Driscoll
Emma Sullivan

Molly James
Peter Walker
Michael Wathen
Mohammad Shafiu Azan Khan

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

RugOBSS Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System

Mar Roca Mora
Bede Ffinian Rowe Davies
Maria João Borlido Oliveira Lima

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Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

SURVEY

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Blue-Cloud2026

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Survey

The Hackathon website offered clear and helpful information.

24 responses

Signing up for the hackathon on Eventornado was very easy

24 responses

Finding a team or additional team members for my team on Eventornado was very easy

24 responses

Joining the Hackathon Discord server (Event Chat) was very easy

24 responses

What are your thoughts on the duration of the 2-week Virtual Warm Up for the Hackathon?

24 responses

The virtual warm-up was thorough, addressing any doubts you had about the hackathon process and providing all the information you needed to participate.

24 responses

[LINK TO THE FULL SURVEY](#)

Survey

The instructions included in the Hack Guide were very clear

24 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

The "Hack Guide" was very useful

24 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

You were satisfied with the coaches and mentors' availability throughout the hackathon

24 responses

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

[LINK TO THE FULL SURVEY](#)

Survey

How do you feel about the 3-day duration of the hackathon?
24 responses

Too short

Too long

The number of deliverables requested during the hackathon was appropriate
24 responses

Too few

Too many

[LINK TO THE FULL SURVEY](#)

Survey

How would you rate your overall satisfaction with the Hackathon?

24 responses

Poor

Great!

Not really

Very much

Would you take part in another hackathon organized by Blue-Cloud?

24 responses

[LINK TO THE FULL SURVEY](#)

Blue-Cloud Hackathon 2025

FEEDBACK ON BLUE-CLOUD SERVICES

Survey: Feedback on Blue-Cloud Services

Full feedback replies on Blue-Cloud service can be found in columns E to H of [this file](#)

BCH 25 Hackathon - Survey (Responses) Share

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100% 123 Roboto 10

Summarise this table

Timestamp	What is your first name?	What is your surname?	What is your hackathon team name?	BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE: How easy was it to use?	BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS: How easy was it to use?	DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE: How easy was it to use?	IDEAS FOR IMPROVING THE SERVICES
01/10/2025 14:06:37	Anna	Mezzapesa	a.mezzap Ingenium	5/10	8/10	7/10	
01/10/2025 14:06:42	Nandini	Gantayat	nandiniga Nautilus	Difficult	Easy to navigate difficult to run as it was resource	Very easy	Cluster based conta
01/10/2025 14:09:32	Mar	Roca	mar.rocaj RugOBSS	The UX could improve by using a more familiar de	Collaborating from workspace was not very intuiti	Data access from the quoted Open-Access reposi	Virtual Machine set r Virtual machine view Different base librari
01/10/2025 14:09:47	Raül	Galdeano Pazos	raul.galde Blume	A bit complicated at the beginning, because we h	We had some problems to access data, but we co	It was not easy, indeed, but we could obtain very i	
01/10/2025 14:11:51	Marjahn	Finlayson	marjahn.f MedSea Investigators	It was not too difficult once we had instructions fr	The instructions made it easier to navigate throug	It was easier to access BEACON once I followed i	
01/10/2025 14:13:00	Fotios	Zapantis	fzapantisj Nautilus	Very Easy	Very Easy	Very Easy	Maybe provide some
01/10/2025 14:13:33	Dolapo Salim	Olatoye	dolaposali Nautilus	Very easy	Very easy	Not too easy	
01/10/2025 14:15:49	P ADITHYA	M NAIK	adithyanal BuildNeo	It was okay. Not too easy to understand.	It was difficult.	It was difficult.	Adding detailed tuto
01/10/2025 14:20:26	Riccardo	Maetzke	riccardom essiHack				
01/10/2025 14:24:19	Wiktoria	Michalska	wiktoria.w DeepZee	Challenging at first, but once it clicked it was easy	Easy, similar to platforms I used in the past	Okay-ish	More intuitive
01/10/2025 14:37:34	Lotte	Pohl	lotte.pohlj TwinTrack	We did not use the Virtual Research Environment	The VLABs were easy to find on the website, less	We didn't use the service for the hackathon - we s	1) Make clear tutori
01/10/2025 14:57:31	Hossam	Eishahaby	hossam.a MusselAlert	Quite user friendly	The resources where available	It takes time to analyze data and use it for decisio	Thank you. Nice Hac
01/10/2025 15:22:29	Aleksandra	Dudkowska	aleksandr CoastBusters	Quite easy	Quite easy	not that easy - it was kind of difficult adapt data fr	Better metadata in V
01/10/2025 15:34:43	Maria Celestina	Henriques	mcelestin DeepZee	As this was my first time participating in such an	Accessing the Virtual Labs was feasible, but i felt	I was able to access the data, but since the tool w	It would be helpfu
01/10/2025 15:48:53	Danil	Mumladze	danil.mur Smiley axolotl	In general easy - but sometimes the platform felt	Accessing virtual labs was easy, the only problem	Quite intuitive, the only problem is the server crash	The aforementioned
01/10/2025 15:49:20	Emilia	Curylo	e00curylo SkadiX	Was quite straightforward	Maybe wish the documentation for vlab would be s	Quite easy	Separate documentat
01/10/2025 15:54:32	Osas	Adeniyi	osasadeni yes				
01/10/2025 15:55:51	Melina	Mortimer	mortimer Nautilus	It was quite easy, but I was not the first time I use	Super easy! The access online when the virtual l	A bit more difficult than the 2 previous questions	Maybe create a

Team: Blume

FEEDBACK ON BLUE-CLOUD

Blue-Cloud is the backbone of MarIA—powerful data access, with room to grow in usability

User Experience

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) was intuitive after a short learning curve.

Having access to multiple datasets in one environment is a major advantage.

Virtual Labs & Workbenches

The Ecosystem Workbench and Fisheries Atlas were particularly useful to combine biological and environmental data.

Clear documentation and tutorials accelerated experimentation.

Data Discovery & Access Service

Easy to identify relevant datasets (e.g., catch records, oceanographic drivers).

Interoperability across sources is a strong asset for predictive modeling.

Ideas for Improvement

A more user-friendly UI for data visualization directly in the VRE.

Simplified API integration to connect Blue-Cloud data streams with external AI models.

Step-by-step onboarding guides for newcomers to reduce the initial learning barrier.

Team: Deepzee

4. Blue-Cloud Data Integration

Current state:

- Best practices for Blue Cloud integration are unclear
- Download CSV files from **Data Discovery and Access Services**
- Manually integrate into our application

Future improvement:

- Enable **API-based integration with authentication** for secure and automated data flow

Team: Deepzee

5. User Experience Feedback

The goal of collecting user experience feedback is to create the platform that will be the most intuitive, informative, and engaging for diverse audiences. We would collect the feedback by short in-app surveys after exploratory sessions, optional feedback button on the map to report confusion, bugs or suggestions. We will also collect anonymous usage data eg. layer toggles, time-slider interactions or map zoom behavior, to understand common patterns and pain points.

Feedback will guide iterative improvements, ensuring the interface is accessible to both experts and non-specialists, while building user trust in the accuracy and educational value of the data.

Action Plan

1. Collect feedback iteratively at alpha, beta, and post-launch stages.
2. Prioritize improvements based on impact (critical usability issues > nice-to-have features).
3. Close the loop with users by communicating how their feedback shaped updates.
4. Maintain a feedback backlog to track requests and ideas for future releases.

Team: Deepzee

6. Virtual Labs Feedback (GlobalFisheriesAtlas)

Swagger page for GRSF API testing

Provides an interactive interface to explore and test the GRSF API endpoints easily, which helps developers and analysts understand the API functionality without writing extra code.

Shiny app (demo) for quick analysis

Offers a user-friendly, interactive dashboard for performing quick data analysis and visualization, making it easier for non-technical users to gain insights.

Jupyter Notebook support

Enables reproducible workflows and advanced data analysis in a familiar environment for data scientists, supporting experimentation and documentation in one place.

Fully open-source

Ensures transparency, encourages community contributions, and allows customization for specific use cases, which is highly valuable for collaborative research and development.

Overall we are very happy with the virtual lab

Team: Deepzee

7. Data Discovery Feedback

- The Data Discovery interface is intuitive and user-friendly, making it easy to navigate and locate datasets. However, the filtering capabilities could be expanded to allow for more precise and efficient data selection.
- Data availability appears to be fragmented, with certain datasets accessible only in specific geographic areas. This limits the comprehensiveness of analysis and may require users to source data from multiple regions manually.
- Once a dataset is requested, the approval process can be time-consuming. Streamlining this workflow or providing clearer expectations around approval timelines would enhance the user experience.
- Additionally, offering an API for dataset ordering and access would significantly improve automation and integration into existing data pipelines. The virtualization features are particularly strong and provide a seamless experience for exploring and interacting with data.

Team:

8. Improvement Suggestions

- Create a mobile app version of our interactive web platform
- Apply AI-powered predictive models climate impact on species distribution
- Promoting citizen science contribution to the web
- Add features like educational modules and gamification to promote knowledge
- Add more layers and one-click analysis
- Improve performance

Team: Blue-Cloud Marine

Feedback on Blue-Cloud Services

- Virtual Labs: Easy to access, strong potential for integration
- Data Discovery: Valuable for multi-source data (but metadata navigation could improve)
- Ideas for Improvement:
More tutorials for first-time users
Easier interoperability between Vlabs
Expanded APIs for seamless external integration.

Team: Jelly Guard

Feedback on Blue-Cloud

Platform UX (VRE): clear workspace structure; smooth SSO onboarding.

VLabs: relevant entry points; useful curated datasets; would benefit from “**quick-start recipes**” for drift modelling.

DD&AS: powerful filters (space/time/keyword); **push-to-VRE** accelerates pipelines.

Ideas to improve: add **example notebooks** for jellyfish-bloom use cases (SST+Chl-a+currents), lightweight **map previews** in DD&AS results, and a **starter template** for publishing to the Data Catalogue/Spatial Repository.

Team: Kraken the code

Feedback

BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE

- 🟢 The platform covers a lot of areas (Science areas and toolsets)
- 🚫 The platform is slow to interact with, particularly during periods that many users are likely to be using it (e.g. 18:00 on hackathon days).
- 🚫 The navigation is not intuitive for a new user
- Key quotes from the team:
 - 🚫 "The experience over the past 12 hours has been almost unusable"
 - 🟡 "It was fine for an hour in the morning"
- 🟢 The shared workspaces are great and really help the team to work together

BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS

- It would be useful to have a summary table of the objective of each VLAB, what data it uses, outputs and its spatial limits
- Sometimes challenging to navigate to the VLAB itself
- VLAB specific feedback:
 1. Vlab2: 🚫 (Very) slow to access data.
 2. Vlab4: 🟢 Easier to interact with. 🚫 Hard coded coordinates are not user friendly. 🚫 Only a narrow subset of data currently available.

DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE:

- 🟢 The shared credentials helped external data access (e.g. CMEMS)

IDEAS FOR IMPROVING BLUE-CLOUD

- Make the relationship between EDITO and Blue cloud clearer? – what is each used for, which data is stored where.
- Allow Blue-Cloud toolsets to run on EDITO too.
- Provide clearer guidance of how external datasets will be used – can we add data with a restrictive licence? How can we control the data throughout its lifecycle?

Team: PhytoNET

Blue-Cloud Platform Feedback

BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE:

- The Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a powerful, centralized platform for collaborative science. The Jupyter-based environment is familiar but has a learning curve for new users.

BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS:

- Navigating the Virtual Labs is intuitive. However, we encountered a significant technical hurdle: a **persistent path error with the Phytoplankton EOV Demonstrator** prevented us from extracting the core dataset for our model.

DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE:

- The service is excellent for discovering a wide array of relevant datasets from providers like Copernicus. It is a great starting point for any ocean-related project.

IDEAS FOR IMPROVING BLUE-CLOUD:

- **Improved Documentation & Troubleshooting:** More detailed tutorials and a known-issues page for Virtual Labs would be very helpful.
- **Streamlined Data Access:** Simplifying the authentication and data download process for specific datasets would accelerate development.

Team: RugOBSS

Feedback and ideas on Blue-Cloud

The UX could **improve** by using a more familiar **design**. Too much information in gateway dashboard and we suggest improving the **old-fashioned appearance**.

Collaborating from workspace was **not very intuitive** to and how to access the different Vlabs jointly was an issue.

- Virtual Machine set up was **slow** and provided **no computing benefits** over local machine.
- Virtual machine viewer of **jupyterlab**, incorrect sizing to screen and **continuous jumping** of view/scroll level.
- Different base libraries included with different virtual Jupyterlabs

Data access from the quoted Open-Access repositories (**EMODNET, Copernicus**) was not clearly explained nor facilitated. **No access** granted to workbenches.

Team: The ALPHA Squad

Feedback on Blue-Cloud's services:

- BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE:
Happy to be on it. But not very easy to find our way. The explanation video's helped the most!
- BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS:
Not easy to get into the Virtual Labs. Missing a 'federated' data catalog over all labs. Missing Naming conventions.
- DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE:
EDITO was way easier to use than the Virtual Labs. The explanation video's helped the most!
- IDEAS FOR IMPROVING BLUE-CLOUD: Any ideas or recommendations you may want to share (optional).
Please consider:
 - **using a custom implementation**
 - **improve documentation**
 - **server seems too big for the current data storage**

Team: EcoSea EO

Feedback to Blue-Cloud services

Platform User Experience

- Interacting with the *Blue Cloud Gateway Dashboard* was not easy at the beginning. Everything was ok once we got familiar. It must be explained explicitly the link between the Vlab and the Workbench.

Virtual Lab

- Yes, I had the objective clear about using *Jupyter Hub* so it was handy. Of course, after I saw the previous sessions. They were very useful.
- I strongly recommend, in *Jupyter Hub*, to add a section for "Install your own environment?". This might support the interoperability and to keep libraries updated.

Data Discovery

- Not handy, I wish I had the results of the VLabs like ChI-a or TRIX Indicators in a section like *Mei Generator*. Also, some libraries were crushing when I was trying to run VLabs. There must be a dedicated site for this a bit more accessible. The EDITO data viewer was very good and helpful. Still, thank you for the previous session, it helped to find easily the TRIX Indicator resources.

Ideas

- I wish the *Jupyter Hub* has a *Deploy* button or a section in Dashboard that works for Deployment or Web Hosting.

Team: Smiley axolotl

Blue-Cloud Platform User Experience & Virtual Labs

Blue-Cloud offers a rich ecosystem of services for marine research, bringing together models, data, and training.

Virtual Labs provide easy access to advanced scientific workflows - very valuable for people who don't know how to code too well (although, it wasn't really an issue for us, since we were a team of Computer Scientists haha).

The training academy was effective for onboarding; tutorials made resources way more approachable for newbies.

Time-saving factor -> since Blue-Cloud provides a lot of "ready to work with" data it saves a bunch of time for researchers and developers to actually make an impact in the world

Team: Smiley axolotl

Data Discovery & Access service

Data discovery was straightforward and well-structured; most needed datasets were available directly.

Metadata standards made integration quite easy.

There happened to be occasional server-side instability
-> e.g. unzipping would crash the server which does
impact your workflow a lot.

Some specialized data had to be extracted from different
data sources (probably due to very specific niche of our use
case).

Team: Smiley axolotl

Ideas to Improve

Refactor the design of the website -> sometimes you get overwhelmed as a new user because the website doesn't have a good structure

Make workbenches available -> mostly, it was just a problem for us because we wanted to use data from one of the workbenches, but unfortunately all of them were private

Have somewhere a dashboard with clear indication what you are currently running right now -> could not personally find it anywhere an overview of the sources I am running (I did see the page with the workspace info, but no info about currently running resources)

Allow users to submit jobs without creating a jupyterhub environment -> due to the latency problems, it is very hard to run and keep track of heavy jobs, hence having a way to submit a job to the server in a json format from the local device would be very nice

When inviting a user when you start typing a name, e.g. "Dani" it will pop up all the names of the people that start with "Dani", but in our consideration it might be a privacy concern

Team: ThermoStatus

Blue-Cloud Platform

- BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE: **The Virtual Research Environment provides a intuitive platform for collaborative and development in harmony with technologies used by the ocean science community.**
- BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS: **The V Labs reunites que main resources for data access and processing, as JupyterHub and Google Cloud Platform, while the Analytics Engine provides the environment for high computational processes.**

The screenshot displays the DataMiner web interface. At the top, there are navigation links: 'go back', 'Access to the Data Space', 'Execute an Experiment', and 'Check the Computations'. Below this, a sidebar on the left shows a tree view with 'Ocean Regimes' expanded. The main content area is titled 'Ocean Regimes Indicator 1.0' and contains a code editor with parameters like 'V_Marine_Env_VIT'. A file browser window is overlaid on the right, showing the path 'MarineEnvironmentalIndicators > notebooks > OceanRegimesIndicator'. The file browser lists 'README.txt' and 'OceanRegimesIndicator.zip' under the 'Name' column. The browser window also shows standard actions: 'New Folder', 'Upload', 'Download', 'Refresh', and 'Delete'.

Team: ThermoStatus

Blue-Cloud Platform

- DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE: **This portal make it possible to research all necessary datasets over a wide range of period with a few steps, making all the process very easy.**
- IDEAS FOR IMPROVING BLUE-CLOUD: **Would be great to couple resources from the Blue-Cloud Platform with HPC services where regional models are being running, which is a desired feature for digital twin of the ocean applications.**

Team: Water Tribe

Blue Cloud Service Improvements

- ✓ More frequent data refresh cycles for key indicators
- ✓ Standardize metadata tags for easier dataset discovery
- ✓ Add pre-built visualization templates to accelerate user adoption
- ✓ Improve and simplify UI for better navigation and understanding

Team: CoastBusters

BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE:

How easy was it for you to access the Virtual Labs and navigate through their services and resources?

In practice, we used Jupyter notebooks in the Marine Environmental Indicators VLab to run our CEI computations, which could then be combined with external datasets (CVI) from EDITO.

Familiarizing with the Virtual Research Environment (VRE) was relatively straightforward thanks to the available tutorials and documentation, but several challenges were observed.

- Registration and access: The single sign-on process worked smoothly, allowing quick entry into the Blue-Cloud Gateway. However, during the final day of the hackathon we experienced intermittent login/access issues.
- Navigation: The structure of V Labs and Workbenches is clear once you explore the "About/Docs" section, but it still took time to locate specific datasets and tools.
- Hands-on use: Launching JupyterHub and accessing notebooks helped us test workflows, but the sample notebooks required significant adaptation and were not immediately "plug & play."
- Learning curve: The system became intuitive after some practice, yet certain Python libraries (e.g. `geopandas.sjoin_nearest`) were not supported, requiring workarounds.

Overall, the VRE offers a good balance between accessibility for new users and flexibility for advanced analyses, but smoother onboarding, stability, and broader library support would further improve the experience.

Team: CoastBusters

BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS:

How easy was it to familiarize yourself with the use of Blue-Cloud's Virtual Research Environment?

Blue-Cloud provides a wide range of tutorials and documentation, which makes onboarding possible. However, browsing these materials and learning all details is very time-consuming. Scientists and marine professionals often do not have the time to study extensive manuals, and they would benefit from faster, more intuitive guidance.

Currently, Virtual Labs are not always clearly described — it is difficult to quickly find what type of data they provide, what outputs can be generated, and especially what the spatial or temporal coverage is. This slows down practical use and limits adoption.

To make the platform truly accessible for a wider community of decision-makers, agencies, and scientists, more user-friendly discovery tools are needed. For example, AI/LLM-based assistants could help users immediately identify relevant datasets or labs without extensive manual search. Faster search, clearer metadata, and concise descriptions would make the environment more attractive for both experts and practitioners who need quick, actionable insights.

Team: CoastBusters

DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE:

How easy was it for you to discover and access data relevant to your solution using Blue-Cloud's Data Discovery & Access service?

Using the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service was overall intuitive and effective, though it required a short familiarization phase.

- Search & filtering – the search engine and filters made it possible to narrow down datasets relevant to coastal erosion and climate impacts, but searching still takes time and is not always straightforward.
- Data diversity – availability of both oceanographic observations and metocean data enabled a more comprehensive approach.
- Integration with VRE – seamless import of selected datasets into the working environment (e.g. notebooks, analyses) significantly accelerated the workflow.
- Metadata clarity – metadata is structured, but not always clear; users cannot easily see the type of data a Virtual Lab offers or its spatial/temporal coverage.
- Added value – the system supports data reusability and enables building custom indicators/indices (e.g. Coastal Erosion Index).

At the same time, we encountered some important limitations:

- EDITO does not allow adding new collections directly.
- GeoJSON dragged onto the EDITO Viewer does not display correctly, and there is no visible option to change or adapt layer formats.

Team: CoastBusters

IDEAS FOR IMPROVING BLUE-CLOUD:

Any ideas or recommendations you may want to share (optional).

Ideas for Improving Blue-Cloud:

- Simplified onboarding – provide short interactive tutorials or guided “first steps” to reduce the learning curve for new users.
- Improved dataset discovery – introduce smarter search options (e.g. by geographic area on a map, thematic tags, or by time period) to make relevant data easier to find.
- User-friendly visualisation – add quick-view tools for basic plotting or map previews before downloading/using data.
- Clearer workflow examples – expand the library of ready-to-use notebooks/workflows showing practical applications (e.g. erosion risk, ecosystem indicators).
- Performance & stability – continue to optimise data loading and notebook execution speed for large datasets.
- AI-based guidance – integrate LLM assistants that can quickly suggest which Virtual Lab or dataset to use, reducing the need for time-consuming manual browsing of documentation.
- Improved publishing in EDITO – enable adding custom collections and fix support for GeoJSON/layer formatting to allow teams to share their own results seamlessly.

Team: essiHack

BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE: How easy was it to familiarize yourself with the use of Blue-Cloud's Virtual Research Environment?

Blue-Cloud V.R.E. purpose is facilitating collaborative research and indeed it was very easy to us familiarizing with its functionalities.

There are plenty of Virtual Labs, Catalog and Training materials to take advantage of, and we've only just begun to scratch the surface.

We really appreciated the fact that any functionality has its own *factsheet* and references to publications and projects, which helps understanding how the single part AND the whole project came to life.

Team: essiHack

DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE: How easy was it for you to discover and access data relevant to your solution using Blue-Cloud's Data Discovery & Access service?

Our idea was to facilitate discovery for Blue-Cloud users, having realized that this aspect was not initially very straightforward, and that's what we did..

.. so the actual answer to this question is:

Very easy...by means of the proposed hackathon idea!

Team: essiHack

BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS: How easy was it for you to access the Virtual Labs and navigate through their services and resources?

We did not have the need to directly use the Virtual Labs or navigate their services and resources, since our challenge (Challenge 4) did not involved them.

Therefore, as far as we have tried it offers a unique powerful open science collaborative platform, but at the moment we haven't explored its full potential.

ON THE OTHER HAND..

.. we found EDITO platform a very rich environment, offering different services to the marine users, we had the chance to test in the Jupiter Hub aspect, finding it quite powerful and user friendly.

Team: Ingenium

Feedback on Blue-Cloud Platform

Our overall experience with the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment was moderately positive, but with several challenges. Familiarization with the platform scored around 6/10: the layout feels somewhat outdated and the software not always intuitive. Each Virtual Lab has a very different structure and level of functionality – in some cases users can perform meaningful operations, while in others the interaction is limited to static graphical outputs rather than access to raw data. Interestingly, we found that even a private Virtual Lab (Aquaculture Monitor) was flagged as available for hackathon use, which created some confusion.

Access to the Virtual Labs was fairly straightforward, although the main difficulties appeared once we tried to work with data in a more advanced way. Discovering and accessing data was generally not difficult, since our use case did not require hidden or very specific datasets. While we did not always find direct data, we were able to identify datasets that allowed us to compute the values we needed.

Looking forward, our main recommendation would be to provide more detailed guides for each Virtual Lab, ensuring that users clearly understand what can be done, what type of data is accessible, and how to move from visualization to real data analysis. This would greatly improve the overall user experience and reduce the learning curve for new users.

Team: Ingenium

Feedback on EDITO

Our first impression of EDITO DataLab is that it is clearly not designed for basic users: a minimum level of technical knowledge is required to navigate its tools and resources effectively. At the same time, the platform shows a modern layout and updated features, and the fact that part of the interface is available also in Italian is a valuable advantage for accessibility.

Compared to Blue-Cloud, EDITO feels more up-to-date and coherent in design, with a smoother integration of services such as the Data Lake, “what-if” simulation scenarios, and Copernicus/EMODnet resources. The datasets are well-structured, but the learning curve remains steep for newcomers, particularly for those approaching without a strong data or oceanographic background.

A potential improvement would be to develop step-by-step tutorials and guided workflows, especially targeted at non-experts or hackathon teams, so that they can quickly move from dataset discovery to concrete applications. Adding use-case templates (e.g. pollution monitoring, aquaculture, coastal management) would make the platform much more engaging and practical.

Overall, we found EDITO to be a robust and promising environment, especially suited for advanced users, but with the potential to become a key tool for a broader community if supported by better onboarding materials.

Team: MedSea Investigators

Challenges & Feedback

- **EDITO PLATFORM:**
 - Our goal was to link the EDITO reprocessed data (.nc files) to the Blue Cloud Virtual Lab. What we were able to do (below) was establish a link in Blue Cloud through EDITO S3 storage.
 - However, running notebooks in the EDITO jupyter notebook platform proved difficult and we kept running into issues with the limited storage provided for the challenge. This said, it proved very difficult to reprocess data and to make the connection between Blue Cloud and EDITO.
 - The only issue observed is that a large number of print statements within the notebook procedures may cause JupyterLab to become unresponsive or crash.
- **IDEAS FOR IMPROVING BLUE-CLOUD:** Any ideas or recommendations you may want to share (optional).
 - Optimize the platform for mobile devices and smaller screens, ensuring accessibility for field researchers.
 - Expand tutorials, case studies, and video guides focused on multi-dataset workflows and combined Virtual Lab usage.

Team: MedSea Investigators

Challenges & Feedback

- **BLUE-CLOUD PLATFORM USER EXPERIENCE:**
 - Our group's experience varied between having a lot of difficulty and medium ease. Previous experience with the chosen application (e.g. Jupyter Notebooks, R Studio, webODV, etc) made it easier use the labs.
 - Workspaces and applications were easier to navigate after watching the live session and having resources to refer to.
- **BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS:**
 - The group's experience varied here again, but the instructions were easier to follow.
 - We found that some backdoor made it difficult to re-run some notebooks, i.e. OHC in the Marine Environmental Indicators
- **DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE:**
 - Using Beacon was easier once the Github was available and instructions were there. Primarily, the YouTube video in the Hack Guide was a great starting point to start understanding where to go to access this data.
 - We had some backdoor difficulty with linking the EDITO data to Blue Cloud

Team: MusselAlert

Feedback:

Navigation challenges: It took significant effort to access the right tools and data in the Blue-Cloud and EDITO platforms

Access issues: We faced repeated errors when trying to connect to EDITO datasets and Virtual Labs, which slowed us down

Difficult to use: The platforms are a little difficult for users with not a lot of programming background. User-friendly step-by-step guides would really help

Rich and diverse datasets: The wide variety of data available helped us refine and strengthen our concept.

Team: SkadiX

Blue-Cloud Virtual Lab (VLab): A Hands-On Experience

Strength: Versatility

The VLab is highly versatile and adaptable, offering a flexible environment that can be configured to fit specific user and project needs.

- Extensive documentation on a VLabs
- Fast access and processing of marine data
- Easily allows to customize datasets and connect them

Area for Improvement: File Management

Navigating the file explorer presents some limitations inherent to cloud-based environments. Operations like cutting/pasting files and bulk importing can be less intuitive compared to a local desktop experience.

- Dependency between datasets and metadata better explained
- Code in notebooks more comments would be helpful

Team: SkadiX

Forward Look: EDITO (Digital Twin of the Ocean)

Opportunity: Powerful Visualization

As a Digital Twin of the Ocean, EDITO offers a powerful, high-level platform for visualizing and contextualizing the complex data products and results generated within the VLab.

Potential: "What-If" Scenario Analysis

EDITO's primary strength lies in its "what-if" simulation capabilities. This would allow the findings from our VLab analysis to be used to model future impacts and support long-term, strategic decision-making for a broader audience.

Team: TwinTrack

Making Blue-Cloud and EDITO even better

Blue-Cloud

- Scientifically well founded applications and data generation processes
- Lack of clarity on what a workbench or VLAB is
- Trouble landing into an actual working/coding environment
- Fisheries atlas is disorienting. This [page](#) should be super visible and accessible

EDITO

- Powerful platform that unites data access and the development of performant online applications
- Readily configurable coding environment we all could collaborate on
- Rapid access to the Data Lake and cloud storage
- Interconnecting multiple services (models, web app, bluecloud code) not easy, but the documentation leads you there
- For our TwinTrack team, deploying a lightweight web application on EDITO worked very successfully

<https://dtotwintrackbluecloudhackathon2025.lab.dive.edito.eu/>

Team: TwinTrack

BLUE-CLOUD VIRTUAL LABS

The TwinTrack Team utilises the *Zoo and phytoplankton EOV products* and the *Global Fisheries Atlas* BlueCloud Virtual Labs. By now, we successfully pulled out data that is useful for the modelling workflow we are developing.

Zoo and phytoplankton EOV products

- This virtual lab is a powerful tool aggregating plankton data and computing interpolated raster files.
- GPU requirement not mentioned in [README.md](#)
- One challenge encountered was discovering that the Julia workflow requires GPU by default. This, unfortunately, was not mentioned in the [README.md](#), which led to some delays as we had to adjust the code to run without GPU support, given that our EDITO workspace does not currently provide access to a GPU, since we don't have access to one in our EDITO workspace.

Global Fisheries Atlas

- Valuable repository that unites fisheries catch data worldwide
- We are slightly confused why there is a [Tuna Atlas](#) and a [Fisheries Atlas](#). The user gets pointed to the Tuna Atlas when clicking the VLAB 'Global Fisheries Atlas' on <https://blue-cloud.org/virtual-labs/global-fisheries-atlas>. It would be clearer if the actual Fisheries Atlas would also be listed on the blue-cloud website.

Team: TwinTrack

DATA DISCOVERY & ACCESS SERVICE

How easy was it for us to discover and access data relevant to your solution using Blue-Cloud's Data Discovery & Access service?

The Global Fisheries Atlas VLAB were very straightforward to access

The Access service however, helped us identifying the Zoo and Phytoplankton EOV products VLAB, which was very helpful

In the future, it would be useful to see the temporal range and resolution, and maybe taxa incorporated in the datasets. This would make identifying relevant datasets even better!

THANK YOU!

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